

Investigating strategies for categorizing electric field pulses associated with return strokes and other lightning-related processes

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Abstract— This study aims to present a preliminary analysis of data recorded by a novel lightning detection network installed in the metropolitan region of Belo Horizonte, Brazil, to evaluate the temporal parameters of bipolar intracloud (IC) pulses and preliminary breakdown (PB) pulses, aiming to enable their separation from pulses related to return strokes (RS). From the evaluation of 300 IC pulses and 300 PB pulses, it was possible to determine that the average total duration of these events is basically the same, being 14.07 and 13.02 μs , respectively, with the main difference between the two being the front time, which on average is about 70% shorter in ICP. A detailed explanation of these phenomena, followed by statistical analyses, is elaborated to identify parameters that will subsequently feed into an automatic classification algorithm.

Keywords— Preliminary breakdown pulses, intracloud pulses, return stroke, electric field, lightning location system, statistical analyses.

I. INTRODUCTION

The characterization of lightning parameters plays an important role for both protection and detection purposes [1]. The time and intensity parameters of return stroke currents, such as the associated peak value and corresponding front and total durations, comprise critical inputs for the design of protection systems. These parameters allow for determining the average extension of the protection systems, collection area, as well as ensuring the components can withstand the stresses produced by the lightning electromagnetic pulses [2], [3], [4].

Electric field waveforms associated with lightning physical processes can also be used for developing protection techniques and for performing lightning detection. The e-field changes and the time elapsed during lightning flashes can be utilized for estimating peak currents and total transferred charges during return strokes [5], [6]. Moreover, the corresponding waveforms can reveal specific features of the various physical processes

occurring during these events, which allows further categorizing them between a cloud flash (IC) or a cloud-to-ground lightning discharge (CGs). For the case of CGs, the e-field also enables distinguishing them between upward and downward events, as well as identifying its corresponding polarity.

From electromagnetic fields measured during lightning flashes, the so-called Lightning Location Systems (LLS) detect and geolocate lightning strikes over large areas with an accuracy of a few hundred meters or better [7], [8]. With the aid of powerful location techniques, these systems can distinguish between intracloud (IC) and cloud-to-ground (CG) discharges, determine the polarity of CG flashes (whether they are positive or negative), and even distinguish between upward and downward CG strokes. This detailed information is important for a wide range of applications, which includes weather forecasting and severe storm monitoring, lightning safety and protection of structures, wildfire prevention and management, and so on.

Despite the advanced state of development of the measurement techniques for lightning electromagnetic fields, as well as the corresponding deployed location methods, it is observed that, in some cases, LLS tend to present some systematic misclassification. This observation is most likely associated with the criteria that each network uses to categorize the events. It is not rare to observe, for instance, IC being commonly misidentified as +CG. This is likely due to the automatic classification criteria employed by the networks, as the corresponding electric field signatures can appear quite similar, leading to their erroneous categorization.

In this regard, addressing these systematic detection issues through refinements in lightning event identification algorithms is an important area of ongoing research to improve

the reliability and accuracy of LLS data for various applications. To present a preliminary contribution to this specific topic, this paper reports an early study of the temporal parameters of the electromagnetic pulses associated with the different processes occurring during leader and channel formation, namely,

- i. *IC pulses (ICP)*: associated with the development of the plasma leader during cloud flashes.
- ii. *CG preliminary breakdown pulses (PBP)*: detected immediately after lightning initiation during cloud-to-ground flashes.
- iii. *CG return stroke pulses (RSP)*: correspond to the fast electric field changes that occurs after the attachment process.

The data on which the statistical study presented in this paper is based was obtained during the 2023-2024 lightning season in Brazil, by a novel detection network installed in the metropolitan region of the city of Belo Horizonte. It is worth remarking that, while existing literature provides some separate statistics on these pulse characteristics, a comprehensive systematic characterization has not been developed for the specific purpose of generating insights into the categorization of lightning events.

The contributions of this study are presented according to the following text structure. After this brief introduction, Section II outlines the instrumentation deployed to acquire the data. Section III presents typical profiles of RSP, ICP and PBP, while Section IV discusses the computed time parameters. The results are presented in Section V and Section VI draws the main conclusions.

II. INSTRUMENTATION

The waveforms and data utilized in this study were all obtained from the deployment of the Fire Neural Network (FNN) HRL™ Detector [9]. This detector features a pair of metallic plate antennas – one for measuring fast electric field variations (HF) and another for slower variations (LF). Since the focus of this study is on evaluating the fast-changing electric field pulses, only the HF signals are considered. The HF channel employs an integrator circuit with a time constant of approximately 1 ms, and the data was sampled at a frequency of 5 MHz during the acquisition process.

Figure 1 illustrates a map of the novel lightning detection network deployed during the 2023-2024 thunderstorm season in Brazil. The network comprises six stations located in the Belo Horizonte metropolitan area: Nova Gameleira, Sabará, Ribeirão das Neves, Betim, Ibirité, and Curvelo. Except for the Curvelo station, the remaining five devices are situated in proximity, with inter-station distances not exceeding 35 km. This configuration enhances the ability to observe initial breakdown pulses within the Belo Horizonte metropolitan region.

Figure 2 showcases the HRL™ Detector deployed at the Curvelo station in Brazil. This detector is a self-contained system, equipped with a battery system powered by solar panels and a mobile internet connection, allowing its autonomous operation.

Fig. 1 The novel detection network installed in Belo Horizonte, Brazil

Fig. 2 FNN HRL™ detector installed in Curvelo, Brazil

III. TYPICAL PROFILES OF ICP, PBP AND RSP

Figures 3 to 5 present some typical profiles of ICP, RSP, and PBP, respectively, as measured by the FNN HRL™ Detectors installed in the novel lightning detection network located in Belo Horizonte. Except for RSP, these pulses are often narrow and bipolar, but they can exhibit variations, such as the presence of multiple peaks, which extend the total duration of these events. The main difference between PBP and ICP is that the former usually appear as a train of pulses, typically lasting around 1 ms [10].

In Figure 4, PBP can be observed mostly between 571 and 571.6. What happens after this time is more related to the effects produced by the leader approaching the ground. Short

pulses can also be identified when the return stroke becomes imminent, but events related to the proximity of the downward leader are not the focus of this study.

Even though it is not depicted in the waveform of Figure 4, it is common for PBP to occur several milliseconds before the return stroke in both negative and positive flashes. However, the observation of these phenomena in +CG within the installed detection network is quite rare. One possible explanation is the inherent characteristic of the electric field produced by the development of the lower part of the +CG bipolar floating leaders, as positives leaders usually propagates continuously [11]. Additionally, the local features of the region under study may contribute to a lower frequency of +CG incidence, such as the typical local cloud structures [12].

Fig. 3 Electric field waveform of an IC pulse (ICP) according to the physics sign convention.

Fig. 4 Electric field signature of a -CG with preliminary breakdown pulses according to the physics sign convention.

As shown in Figures 3 and 5, the waveforms of ICPs and PBPs exhibit some similarities, typically presenting an initial peak followed by a decay that causes an overshoot (or undershoot for opposite polarities) before returning to the initial value. Given the similarity of these waveforms, in addition to the traditional parameters assessed in the literature (rise time and total duration), several other temporal parameters can be evaluated to establish criteria for distinguishing between ICPs and PBPs.

Fig. 5 Electric field waveform of a CG preliminary breakdown pulses (PBP) according to the physics sign convention.

IV. COMPUTED TIME PARAMETERS

Figure 6 highlights the parameters evaluated for each waveform in the dataset acquired during the development of this work. A detailed characterization of each time parameter is presented in the following lines.

Fig. 6 IC pulse with eight of the evaluated parameters marked

- a) $T_{r1\ 50\%}$: Time to reach 50% of maximum amplitude on the first pulse. This is more relevant in RS analysis, but it will be evaluated to establish differentiation criteria for the pulses.
- b) T_{r1} : Time elapsed between the beginning of the first pulse and the corresponding peak.
- c) $T_{f1\ 50\%}$: Time elapsed to decay to 50% of maximum amplitude on the first pulse.
- d) T_{f1} : Time elapsed to decay to its initial value.
- e) $T_{r2\ 50\%}$: Time elapsed to reach 50% of maximum amplitude on the second (overshoot) pulse.
- f) T_{r2} : Time elapsed to reach maximum amplitude on the second pulse.
- g) $T_{f2\ 50\%}$: Time elapsed to decay to 50% of maximum amplitude on the second pulse.
- h) T_{f2} : Time elapsed for the second pulse to return to its initial value.

In addition to these parameters, the overall pulse duration and the ratio between the amplitude of the first peak and any

subsequent overshoot/undershoot during the decay were also assessed to further characterize these waveforms. For the events whose PBP were evaluated, the slow front duration (see [7], [13]) and rise times (slow front + fast transition) of the return strokes were also computed, allowing for a direct comparison of the RS to the other pulse types. It is important to note that the RS computed parameters have significantly lower statistical significance compared to the other pulses, as the 300 evaluated PBPs were observed across only 34 flashes. Furthermore, due to the proximity of the detector, sensor saturation occurred in 12 cases, preventing peak observation and consequently not allowing the rise time to be calculated.

It is important to note that the distance between the lightning leaders (or the ground termination point) and the electric field sensors can influence the measured waveform parameters to a certain degree. To illustrate this, e-field records of a specific negative cloud-to-ground flash detected by 3 different stations are considered, as depicted in Figure 7, which also indicates the lightning strike location with a red star marker and 40-km radius circles centered at each station. The event under consideration occurred 16.1 km from Betim, 31.5 km from Sabará, and 34.8 km from Ribeirão das Neves.

Fig. 7 Map showing the relative distances among the stations of Ribeirão das Neves, Sabará and Betim, and the detected negative cloud-to-ground flash.

Figure 8 presents the return stroke electric field waveforms recorded at each station. The observed differences in the return stroke initiation time can be attributed to the varying distances between the ground strike location and the individual sensors. Additionally, the computed rise times of the electric field pulses exhibit slight variations between the stations. These differences can be explained by the dominant electric field components at each measurement distance, as well as the propagation effects experienced by the electromagnetic signals traveling from the strike point to the respective sensors. It is important to highlight, however, that these differences typically do not exceed 5%.

To maintain a consistent reference point, all the pulses whose time parameters were analyzed in this work were recorded at the Ribeirão das Neves station, during a single thunderstorm that occurred on February 7, 2024. In total, approximately 600 pulses were individually examined and characterized. Half of these pulses were associated with PBP, while the remaining half were ICP. These pulses were obtained through the evaluation of 58 lightning flashes, 34 of which being CG, and the other 24 corresponding to IC.

Fig. 8 A return stroke pulse of a single event as recorded in three different stations (Betim, Sabará, and Ribeirão das Neves)

V. RESULTS

From the analyzed waveforms, some general features can be highlighted. Preliminary breakdown pulses typically exhibit durations ranging from 20 to 100 μs , with an average duration of 60 μs . In cases where these pulses are bipolar, the first peak is consistently narrower than the second. Additionally, the typical interval between successive preliminary breakdown pulses is 70 to 130 μs . In contrast, intracloud pulses tend to

have longer durations, typically between 50 and 80 microseconds, and much larger interpulse intervals, reaching 600 to 800 μs . This is consistent with previous reported statistics, as summarized in [7].

Tables I and II provide a summary of the statistical analysis performed on the parameters of PBP and ICP, respectively. In addition to the geometric mean, the median values, and the standard deviation of the time parameters highlighted in Figure 6, the total duration and the ratio between the first peak value and the overshoot after the decay are also reported.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS COMPUTED FOR PBP

Parameter	PRELIMINARY BREAKDOWN PULSES		
	Geometric mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Total duration (μs)	13.015	7.137	12.503
Ratio (P_{k1}/P_{k2})	6.474	4.275	7.865
$T_{r1\ 50\%}$ (μs)	3.406	1.295	5.007
T_{r1} (μs)	4.418	2.000	5.791
$T_{r1\ 50\%}$ (μs)	1.282	0.776	1.653
T_{r1} (μs)	2.929	1.991	3.075
$T_{r2\ 50\%}$ (μs)	1.135	0.500	2.116
T_{r2} (μs)	2.111	1.050	3.005
$T_{r2\ 50\%}$ (μs)	1.431	0.500	2.133
T_{r2} (μs)	3.556	1.200	5.578

TABLE II
PARAMETERS COMPUTED FOR ICP

Parameter	INTRACLOUD PULSES		
	Geometric mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Total duration (μs)	14.073	9.000	14.494
Ratio (P_{k1}/P_{k2})	6.046	2.732	13.476
$T_{r1\ 50\%}$ (μs)	1.897	0.700	4.074
T_{r1} (μs)	3.093	1.500	4.734
$T_{r1\ 50\%}$ (μs)	1.602	0.800	1.910
T_{r1} (μs)	2.928	1.600	3.125
$T_{r2\ 50\%}$ (μs)	1.339	0.700	1.643
T_{r2} (μs)	2.713	1.660	2.756
$T_{r2\ 50\%}$ (μs)	2.096	1.500	2.490
T_{r2} (μs)	5.339	3.000	7.579

Overall, the computed time parameters are shorter than those reported in literature [10], [14]. This might be associated with the decision of analyzing only pulses with no double peaks. In terms of the average total duration values, both PBP and ICP exhibited similar times, differing primarily in the rise time, which was 30% shorter in IC pulses.

Table III indicates the parameters computed for the return stroke pulses. Although this specific dataset does not present a high degree of statistical significance, due to the limited sample size, they show a trend in the rise time of the recorded RS. The slow front time is easily identified when analyzing the obtained waveforms and generally represents 40 to 50 percent of the peak value [3]. The total rise time highlights the similarity of the values found with the other pulses, especially the PBP.

TABLE III
PARAMETERS COMPUTED FOR RSP

Parameter	RETURN STROKE PULSES		
	Geometric mean	Median	Standard Deviation
Slow front (μs)	3.800	3.400	1.421
Rise time (μs)	5.254	4.900	1.934

A preliminary statistical analysis was conducted to model the rise time and total duration parameters of PBP and ICP, which are considered the most critical variables in this study. Upon evaluating the distributions that best fit the acquired data, the lognormal distribution was found to provide the closest fit, as denoted by the histograms presented along this section.

Figures 9 and 10 present the Probability Density Function (PDF) and the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) for the rise time and total duration of PBPs. The computed mean and standard deviation of the lognormal distribution for the rise time were $\mu = 0.823$ and $\sigma = 1.150$, respectively. For the pulse total duration, the corresponding lognormal distribution parameters were $\mu = 2.153$ and $\sigma = 0.943$. From the CDF plots, the inferred median values for the rise time and total duration were 1.64 μs and 9.74 μs , respectively.

Fig. 9 Fitted probability density function (PDF) overlaid on the data histogram (a) and cumulative distribution function (CDF) of PBPs rise time (b).

Fig. 10 Fitted probability density function (PDF) overlaid on the data histogram (a) and cumulative distribution function (CDF) of PBPs total duration (b).

The same statistical modelling process has been carried out for the ICPs. The corresponding results are shown in Figures 11 and 12 for both parameters, rise time and total duration, respectively. The computed mean and standard deviation of the

lognormal distribution for the rise time were $\mu = 0.492$ and $\sigma = 1.090$, respectively. For the pulse total duration, the corresponding parameters were $\mu = 2.276$ and $\sigma = 0.836$. From the CDF plots, the inferred median values for the rise time and total duration were $1.64 \mu\text{s}$ and $8.61 \mu\text{s}$, respectively.

Fig. 11 Fitted PDF overlaid on the data histogram (a) and CDF of ICP rise time (b).

Fig. 12 Fitted PDF overlaid on the data histogram (a) and CDF of ICP total duration (b).

A comparative analysis reveals that, despite the average parameters being quite similar between the two pulse types, there is an evident difference in their statistical behavior. Specifically, the times associated with intracloud pulses are concentrated within a narrower time range compared to the preliminary breakdown pulses. This observation suggests that the differences in the statistical distributions of the pulse parameters could potentially serve as a useful strategy for automatically distinguishing between IC and PB pulse types.

VI. FINAL REMARKS

Although this initial analysis was based on a limited dataset of 600 pulses from a single thunderstorm, it has nevertheless allowed for a preliminary characterization of the parameters associated with both CG preliminary breakdown and IC pulses recorded in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte, Brazil. The goal was to build an initial database of these lightning event characteristics, including parameters that are not widely reported in the literature but may have potential to contribute to the separation and classification of different pulse types.

Regarding the most relevant time parameters, similar average values were found for the total duration of PBP and ICP. However, for the rise time, the average values for ICP were observed to be about twice as fast compared to PBP, especially the time elapsed to decay to 50% of maximum amplitude on the first pulse. Additionally, the dataset was found to fit well to lognormal distributions, which is an interesting observation given that many other lightning-related parameters are also known to follow this statistical distribution.

The next steps of this study will focus on expanding the database to enable the development of artificial intelligence-based algorithms for lightning categorization that can be fed with this enhanced information on pulse characteristics. This also includes a systematic evaluation of the parameters of more return stroke pulses.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support and resources provided by the Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG) for this research project. Additionally, the authors are grateful for the financial support received from the Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG) through grant number PCE-00106-24.

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